

Enhance the Capacity of University Lecturers in the Context of Educational Innovation and Integration

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Abstract

This article focuses on analyzing the role of enhancing the capacity of university lecturers in the process of educational reform and international integration. The research aims to assess the current state of lecturer capacity, identify influencing factors, and propose appropriate development solutions. Data was collected through surveys and interviews with lecturers at several universities in Vietnam. The results show that many lecturers are still limited in innovating teaching methods, applying technology, and conducting scientific research. The article proposes practical measures such as developing competency-based training programs, promoting self-learning, and fostering an academic community. Improving lecturer capacity is a key factor in ensuring the quality of education and meeting the requirements of sustainable educational development.

Keywords: Faculty competence, professional development, higher education, training, international integration.

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Introduction

In the context of higher education facing comprehensive reform demands, the role of lecturers is becoming increasingly important and decisive for the quality of training. However, the reality at many higher education institutions in Vietnam shows that the capabilities of lecturers are still uneven, especially in areas such as innovative teaching methods, application of technology, and scientific research capacity. Many lecturers do not have the opportunity to access in-depth training programs and lack a positive academic environment for professional development. Given this situation, enhancing the capacity of university lecturers is an urgent requirement to meet the goals of educational reform and international integration. This article focuses on analyzing the current situation, its

causes, and proposing solutions for developing lecturer capacity in a comprehensive and sustainable manner.

Materials and Methods

To achieve the research objectives, this paper uses a mixed-method approach, combining qualitative and quantitative methods to ensure the comprehensiveness and reliability of the collected data.

Quantitative Methods

The research team developed a survey questionnaire focusing on faculty competency groups such as teaching, research, information technology, foreign language, and professional development. The questionnaire was distributed to 230 faculty and administrative staff working at five universities in southern Vietnam. Survey

data was processed and analyzed using descriptive statistics and comparative analysis techniques.

Qualitative Method

Semi-structured interviews (a qualitative data collection method using a prepared list of topics or open-ended questions) were conducted with 225 lecturers and 5 training administrators to explore their perspectives and practical experiences related to enhancing lecturer capacity. The interview content was coded and analyzed using content analysis methods. In addition, the article also refers to national and international documents and reports related to the development of university faculty, in order to compare and draw lessons relevant to the Vietnamese education context.

Results

Theoretical Basis

University faculty competence is a multidimensional concept, reflecting the comprehensive knowledge, skills, attitudes, and professional qualities necessary to effectively perform teaching, research, management, and community service tasks within the higher education environment. According to UNESCO (2004), faculty members need to meet the following main competency groups: professional competence, pedagogical competence, information technology competence, scientific research competence, and professional development competence.

Furthermore, the TPACK (Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge – Mishra &

Koehler, 2006) model also emphasizes the connection between subject matter knowledge, pedagogical methods, and technology in modern teaching. This model is particularly suitable in the context of higher education undergoing digital transformation, requiring lecturers not only to master their subject matter but also to integrate technology and innovate teaching methods.

In Vietnam, the Ministry of Education and Training has also issued a framework of standards for university lecturer titles (Circular 40/2020/TT-BGDĐT), which clearly stipulates criteria regarding educational qualifications, professional competence, scientific research, professional ethics, and foreign language and information technology skills.

From the above arguments, it can be seen that the development of lecturers' capabilities needs to be approached comprehensively, linked to professional standards, and at the same time in line with the context of educational reform and the trend of international integration.

Current State of University Lecturer Competence

The survey results show that the capabilities of university lecturers in Vietnam are currently limited and vary significantly across different educational institutions. Although the majority of lecturers meet professional standards (over 95% hold a master's degree or higher), their ability to meet new requirements in teaching, research, and international integration remains low.

Table 1. Teaching Competence of the Lecturers

Good teaching skills	Completely disagree.		Disagree		Neutral / Undecided		Agree		Totally agree	
	N0	%	N0	%	N0	%	N0	%	N0	%
Design and develop lesson plans.	12	5,16	25	10,75	117	50,3	39	16,77	37	15,91
Applying active learning methods	13	5,59	22	9,46	125	53,75	41	17,63	29	12,47
Utilizing technology and teaching aids.	12	5,16	10	4,3	102	43,86	77	33,11	39	16,77
Pedagogical communication	13	5,59	14	6,02	84	36,12	72	30,96	47	20,21

and classroom management										
Evaluating and providing feedback on learning outcomes.	14	6,02	23	9,89	88	37,84	63	27,09	42	18,06

Source: The Author

From the results in the table above, we can see that teaching competence in general is a very necessary skill requiring flexibility, sensitivity, and creativity from the lecturer, but the application of active teaching methods is still limited. Only about 55.75% of the surveyed instructors said they regularly apply active, learner-centered teaching methods. Many still use traditional lecture methods, rarely updating

to new teaching techniques such as project-based learning, case-based learning, or digital integration.

Furthermore, only 18.06% completely agree with the assessment and feedback on learning that are unclear and lack a developmental orientation for learners.

Table 2. Information Technology Capabilities

Good IT skills	completely disagree.		Disagree		Neutral / Undecided		Agree		Totally agree	
	N0	%	N0	%	N0	N0	%	N0	%	N0
Proficiency in using office software and teaching aids.	22	9,46	35	15,05	117	50,31	39	16,77	17	7,31
Competence in designing and implementing e-learning courses	17	7,31	35	15,05	127	54,61	35	15,05	16	6,88
Utilize online learning platforms and learning management systems (LMS).	17	7,31	35	15,05	129	55,47	41	17,63	12	5,16
Application of IT in testing and evaluating learning outcomes.	14	6,02	37	15,91	125	53,75	35	15,05	19	8,17
The ability to learn independently and update new technologies in teaching.	23	9,89	25	10,75	117	50,31	40	17,2	27	11,61

Source: The Author

The survey indicates that many lecturers have limited proficiency in using office software and teaching support tools, with only 7.31% out of 100% demonstrating good skills. Furthermore, 55.47% are undecided or neutral. Basic IT skills, such as PowerPoint presentations and online class management, are still lacking, with a very

low percentage (6.88%) being unproficient in digital lesson design tools, e-learning, or learning data analysis. Approximately 55.47% of instructors reported hesitation when implementing lectures on online platforms or designing multimedia content. The use of tools such as LMS, AI, or learning data remains basic.

Updating to new technologies for teaching is still limited, with only 11.61% successfully implementing this aspect.

Table 3. The Scientific Research Capacity of Faculty Members

Good scientific research capabilities	completely disagree.		Disagree		Neutral / Undecided		Agree		Totally agree	
	N0	%	N0	%	N0	N0	%	N0	%	N0
Ability to identify and formulate research topics	17	7,31	21	9,03	107	46,01	37	15,91	48	20,64
Skills in conducting research and collecting data	19	8,17	22	9,46	113	48,59	30	12,9	47	20,21
Ability to analyze and process research data	41	17,63	23	9,89	110	47,3	33	14,19	23	9,89
Skills in writing scientific papers and publishing research results.	19	8,17	21	9,03	115	49,45	31	13,33	46	19,78
Participate in academic activities and research development.	25	10,75	27	11,61	97	41,71	47	20,21	34	16,62

Source: The Author

The majority of lecturers have the ability to identify and develop research topics. However, this percentage is still low, with 7.31% of lecturers lacking this ability. Skills in conducting research and collecting data, as well as the ability to analyze and process research data, also show unsatisfactory results. Many lecturers (49.45%)

still struggle with the skills of writing scientific papers and publishing research results, particularly in topic development, research design, and paper publication. This indicates that scientific research skills have not received adequate investment and lack long-term development direction.

Table 4. Foreign Language Proficiency of Lecturer

Good foreign language skills	completely disagree.		Disagree		Neutral / Undecided		Agree		Totally agree	
	N0	%	N0	%	N0	N0	%	N0	%	N0
Skills in reading and understanding specialized documents in a foreign language.	14	6,02	35	15,05	125	53,75	27	11,61	29	12,47
Academic writing skills in a foreign language	29	12,47	44	18,92	121	52,03	21	9,03	15	6,45
Listening and comprehension skills for specialized content in a foreign language.	36	15,48	38	16,34	115	49,45	27	11,61	14	6,02

Professional communication and presentation skills in a foreign language.	31	13,33	49	21,7	127	54,61	28	12,04	15	6,45
The level of application of foreign languages in teaching and research.	38	16,34	51	21,93	107	46,1	21	9,03	13	5,59

Source: The Author

The English proficiency of lecturers remains a major barrier to international integration. 24.08% of lecturers demonstrated very good or excellent reading comprehension of specialized materials in a foreign language. However, the percentage of lecturers with very low listening comprehension skills in a foreign language was 15.48%. Many people still rely on translated materials and do not regularly follow

international academic sources, leading to limitations in accessing new knowledge. This is considered a very low percentage compared to the increasingly high demands of universities in the trend of integration. Professional communication and presentation skills in foreign languages, and the level of application of foreign languages in teaching and research, are still quite low.

Table 5. Faculty's Professional Development Capabilities

Good career development potential	completely disagree.		Disagree		Neutral / Undecided		Agree		Totally agree	
	N0	%	N0	%	N0	N0	%	N0	%	N0
Self-learning and updating professional knowledge.	13	5,59	21	9,03	107	46,01	51	21,93	38	16,34
Participate in professional development and training courses	12	5,16	20	8,6	106	45,58	53	22,79	39	16,77
Engage in academic and professional activities.	13	5,59	21	9,03	147	63,21	61	26,23	68	29,24
Self-assessment and adjustment of professional activities	8	3,44	16	6,88	77	33,11	59	25,37	72	30,96
Develop a long-term career development plan.	11	4,73	19	8,17	113	48,59	55	23,65	42	18,06

Source: The Author

The self-learning and self-improvement capabilities of lecturers are uneven. A portion of lecturers lack personal career development plans, do not proactively participate in training courses, professional seminars, or update on new educational trends; as many as 13.76% have no plan and are not proactive. Many universities

lack mechanisms to mandate or encourage continuous learning and professional development (CPD). Professional self-assessment remains weak, with approximately 12% of faculty members opting for "completely disagree" or "disagree." Regarding the content of long-term professional development planning, a

relatively high percentage still lack clear direction. Overall assessment: University lecturers today are under immense pressure to meet the demands of educational reform and international integration. While possessing strong professional backgrounds, many still struggle with adapting to technology, foreign languages, and scientific research capabilities. This highlights the urgent need for professional development, retraining, and the establishment of mechanisms to support long-term career advancement for lecturers.

Furthermore, the current situation reveals inequality in opportunities for capacity development between urban and rural schools, and between key public schools and smaller training institutions. Some lecturers, despite their high learning spirit, still face difficulties due to a lack of resources, professional support, or an underdeveloped academic environment. Based on the analysis of lecturer capacity in the previous section, which is affected by many multifaceted factors, it can be divided into the following main groups:

Policies and Mechanisms for Training and Professional Development

The biggest obstacle is the lack of clear policies and synchronized mechanisms in faculty training and development. Many educational institutions have not yet developed or implemented appropriate continuing professional development (CPD) programs, nor are there mandatory regulations on competency standards and periodic faculty evaluation. This makes capacity building undirected and unsystematic.

Support Resources and Work Environment

Infrastructure, teaching equipment, and information technology have not been invested in comprehensively, especially in universities in remote and disadvantaged areas. The academic environment lacks encouragement for research and international cooperation, which also limits the motivation and opportunities for faculty development.

Personal Awareness and Motivation

Many lecturers are not fully aware of the importance of capacity building in the context of

educational reform. Some are passive in self-study, updating their knowledge, or participating in training courses. Motivation for career development is low due to a lack of clear practical benefits or due to the pressure of teaching and management work.

Access to Technology and Learning Resources

The application of technology in teaching requires instructors to possess IT skills and the ability to design digital lessons. However, many instructors struggle to access new tools due to a lack of formal training and supporting resources. Furthermore, the lack of high-quality and up-to-date academic materials also hinders their ability to conduct research and innovate teaching methods.

Foreign Language and International Integration

Foreign languages, especially English, are key to expanding opportunities for international cooperation and accessing new knowledge. However, surveys show that the percentage of lecturers with good foreign language skills is low, leading to limitations in participating in conferences, publishing internationally, and updating advanced research.

Solutions to Enhance the Capacity of University Lecturers

To meet the demands of higher education reform and international integration, enhancing faculty capacity needs to be implemented comprehensively, synchronously, and with a long-term strategy. Below are specific solutions, along with objectives and implementation methods.

Develop and Implement a Continuous Professional Development (CPD) Program for Faculty Members

Objective: To help lecturers regularly update their professional knowledge, modern teaching methods, technological skills, and foreign language skills, thereby improving the quality of training and research.

How to do it:

- The CPD program is designed to be diverse, encompassing in-person courses, online courses, and workshops.
- A specific competency framework is established as a basis for evaluating and developing faculty.
- A system of incentives and rewards/punishments is implemented to encourage faculty participation in professional development activities.
- Regular competency assessments and individual development plans are created for faculty members.

Investing in Facilities and Technology to Support Teaching

Objective: To provide faculty with a modern environment and tools to apply information technology in teaching, enhancing students' learning experience.

How to do it:

- Equip classrooms with smart learning systems, online learning platforms, teaching support software, and multimedia equipment.
- Organize training courses on technology usage skills for lecturers.
- Build a rich and up-to-date digital library and electronic learning resources.

Strengthening Support for Scientific Research and International Cooperation

Objective: To enhance the research and international publication capabilities of faculty members, contributing to improving the prestige and quality of university education.

How to do it:

- Provide funding and time for faculty members to participate in research and international conferences.
- Establish modern research labs and centers to support the writing of international publications.

- Support specialized foreign language training and academic writing skills.
- Develop collaborative faculty exchange programs with foreign universities.

Create a Work Environment that Encourages Professional Development

Objective: To motivate and encourage faculty members to actively participate in innovation in teaching and research.

How to do it:

- Establish a transparent and fair reward system based on teaching achievements, research, and contributions to the university.
- Build a positive academic culture that supports experience sharing and internal collaboration.
- Organize professional forums and clubs for exchange, learning, and capacity building.

Enhancing Foreign Language Proficiency and Soft Skills for Lecturers

Objective: To help lecturers proactively access international knowledge, improve teaching effectiveness, and integrate globally.

How to do it:

- Organize intensive foreign language training courses, especially academic English.
- Develop soft skills training programs such as communication skills, time management, and problem-solving.
- Encourage faculty to participate in cultural exchange and international activities.

Conclusion

Enhancing the capacity of university lecturers is a key factor in ensuring educational quality, promoting teaching innovation, and meeting the demands of international integration. Surveys and analyses reveal that current lecturers still have limitations in many areas, such as modern teaching methods, scientific research, information technology application, foreign language proficiency, and personal professional development. These limitations highlight the urgent need for a long-term training and

development strategy, diversifying professional development methods, and creating appropriate incentives and support mechanisms. Investing appropriately in improving lecturer capacity not only enhances the quality of education but also significantly contributes to the sustainable development of the higher education system.

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